

The Role of Emotional Regulation on Self-Acceptance of the Inmates

Utami. Maghfiratul septi¹, Hasnida², Saragih, Juliana I³

^{1,2,3}Department of Clinical Psychology, Universitas Sumatera Utara, Medan, Indonesia, 20155

Abstract— *The study was conducted to determine the role of emotional regulation on self-acceptance of inmates. The research method used is a quantitative method using the cognitive emotion regulation questionnaire (CERQ) scale and self-acceptance scale. The results of the study were the role of emotional regulation on self-acceptance of inmates. The results of the relationship are shown by the coefficient value $R = 0.160$, and the P value is 0.005 ($P < 0.05$), indicating regulation of emotions can affect the variables of self-acceptance of inmates.*

Keywords— *Emotional regulation, self acceptance, inmates.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Prisoners are convicts who undergo criminal acts in the Penitentiary (RI Law No.12 Th.1995 concerning Correctional Article 1 paragraph 7). Correctional Institutions (Lapas) are places to carry out coaching for prisoners and correctional students (RI Law No.12 Th.1995 concerning Correctional Article 1 paragraph 2).

The increasing number of crimes occurring in the territory of Indonesia has led to an increasing number of perpetrators of crimes that have been decided by judges to undergo a period of detention in prisons (Lapas) and state detention centers (detention centers). According to Al Abrar (2016), a study of Indonesian inmates in January to June 2015, within a period of half a year (6 months) the number of prisoners increased by 23 thousand people throughout Indonesia, until October 2015 the number of prisoners throughout Prisons and Detention Centers reached 160,722 people, the number increased to more than 180 thousand inmates in April 2016. After three years the number of prisoners increased by 30 thousand people with various types of crimes. In 2018 the number of prisoners increased to 230 thousand. This is a phenomenon that must be resolved so that it can be minimized (Ministry of Law and Human Rights, Penitentiary News, 2018)

The study conducted by Luh Putu (2017) said the verdicts that had been handed down by the court against individuals who committed criminal offenses resulted in the temporary loss of individual freedom with a new status, namely as inmates. Status as a prisoner is something that is not easy for individuals who have never dealt with the law. Automatically his life will be temporarily kept away from the community in accordance with the crime he committed.

Another study conducted by Lawrence and Andrew (2004) explained that there are risk factors in the prison environment that affect the psychology of prisoners in prison, among others: overcrowding, various forms of violence, lack of privacy, lack of meaningful activity, isolation from social

networks, insecurity about future prospects, and inadequate health services, especially mental health services in prisons.

Research conducted by Ray (Christopher, Yvonne, Dermot, 2014) on prisoners who will approach the period of freedom, a bad stigma from the environment has an impact on physiological responses (faster heart beat, cold sweat) that affect individual emotions. Research conducted by Early Childhood (2015) states that good regulation of emotions causes individuals to be able to reduce the negative emotions that they feel that will later make individuals have good self-acceptance. Based on the phenomenon that shows that prisoners are vulnerable to stress and stress, prisoners need the ability to regulate emotions well, because regulation of emotions is related to an ability to control emotional impulses and behavior as a way of expressing emotions to suit and be accepted by their environment (Thompson, 1994).

Based on research conducted by Yogev Kivity, Maya Tamir, and Jonathan D. Huppert (2016) stated that other factors that influence self-acceptance, namely emotion, good emotional regulation can influence good self-acceptance and have a positive correlation. In line with the research conducted by Allison S. Troy, Amanda J. Shallcross, Anna Brunner, Rachel Friedman, Markera C. Jones (2017) states that regulation of good emotions can affect good self-acceptance which has an impact on the physiological individual, emotional regulation is effective in accepting yourself. Another study conducted by Hiroshi (2011) states that emotion regulation has a positive relationship to self-acceptance in all types of groups, both men and women. Research conducted by Alice Diedrich, Michaela Grant, Stefan G. Hofmann, Wolfgang Hiller, Matthias Berking (2014) states that emotion regulation has a positive correlation with depressed individuals' self-acceptance, positive regulation of emotions can restore moods to be calmer.

Barrett, Gross, Christensen and Benvenuto (2007) research conducted on inmates in California said that to overcome the pressure experienced by inmates it was necessary to control emotions. For that prisoners must be able to have the ability to control their emotions in order to remain effective and effective in pressure, this ability is called emotional regulation. Good emotional regulation will certainly help inmates in facing difficult and stressful times in detention. Maladaptive negative emotions will become more positive and adaptive (Gross, 2007). Research conducted by Jessica (2013) related to the characteristics of prisoners with depressive symptoms in prisons, namely: age, crime, sentencing sentence, length of sentence that has been served, and the number of family visits, family support affects the emotions of

individuals who can inhibit depression symptoms appear on teenagers while in prison.

Based on the results of research from Loweinstein (in Gross, 2007) regulation of good emotions can provide positive experiences for individuals. This positive experience will make individuals feel positive emotions and feelings in their lives. Emotional regulation is able to turn negative emotions into positive ones. Gross and Thompson (2007) say that good emotional regulation ability can help prisoners overcome self-blame, emotional reactions, and reduce negative views due to emotional experiences. Good emotional regulation can reduce the negative emotions that are felt which will make someone have a good self-acceptance. A good self-acceptance of oneself will bring positive thoughts which it will be able to form a positive self-concept also for individuals because self-acceptance is an individual process to achieve a self-concept (Putri & Hamidah, 2012).

One example that prisoners do not have positive emotion regulation can be seen based on personal interviews conducted by researchers to prisoners H (34 years):

"In this prison, Sis, I feel I'm getting angry easily, I'm not calm, Sis. I thought about how my wife's son was at home, where they ate, the length of my punishment period was stressful for me, Sis, yeah, I'm dizzy, Sis, I want to destroy all this, Sis, if I don't let go of emotion, I'm trembling, my cold sweat. That's why I prefer to be alone, Sis, but even this person (friend and prison officer) likes to intervene with me, I sit alone called, cry, tell me to come, it's dizzy, Sis. Since I was here, my wife and daughter have never come, Sis, miss me. Ya Allah "(Personal interview, August 23, 2018)

The results of the interview above show that when a person is in criminal law and becomes a prisoner, he will make a drastic change of behavior to the prisoner himself. Feelings of shame, inferiority, not being noticed, not being loved, because there is no support from the people closest to them. In addition, feeling easily offended, angry because the pressure from the environment of fellow prisoners who get a visit made inmates unable to control the emotions they felt.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Study

Emotional Regulation

Gross (2007) states that emotion regulation is a strategy that is carried out consciously or unconsciously to maintain, strengthen or reduce one or more aspects of emotional responses, namely emotional and behavioral experiences. Individuals who have emotional regulation can maintain or enhance emotions that they feel both positive and negative. In addition, individuals can reduce their emotions both positively and negatively.

Characteristics of Emotional Regulation

Goleman (2004) suggests five skills in emotional regulation abilities: Self control, in the sense of being able to effectively manage destructive emotions and impulses, Having good interpersonal relationships with others, Having a cautious attitude, Having adaptability, Flexibility means in handling changes and challenges, higher tolerance for

frustration Having a positive view of themselves and their environment.

Aspects Regulatory of Emotion

Emotional regulation aspects revealed by Gross and John (2003) Emotional regulation using two dimensions, namely Reappraisal and Suppression. Reappraisal is a cognitive change that involves individuals to change the way they think about situations that can potentially emit emotions so they can change their emotional influence. Reappraisal is a focused focused strategy that occurs earlier before the tendency of an emotional response to be fully activated and to change behavior (Gross & John, 2003).

III. METHOD

The subjects to be examined in this study were inmates in the class IIa Central Aceh remand center, totaling 288 inmates. The sampling technique used is Probability Sampling. Probability Sampling is a sampling technique that provides equal opportunities for each member of the population to be chosen as a sample member (Sugiyono, 2012).

The data collection method in this study is to use a scale. Scale is a tool that measures constructs or psychological concepts that describe aspects of individual personality. The use of scale aims to get subjective answers from the subject by placing responses at points that are continuum and stimulus given in the form of statements (Azwar, 2012).

This item's different power test is done by computing the correlation coefficient between the score distribution in each item with the test total score itself, using the reliability analysis application in SPSS so that the total corrected item coefficient is obtained. Furthermore, all items that reach a correlation coefficient of at least 0.28 are considered to have satisfactory differential power. Aitem which has a value of $r_x < 0.28$ is interpreted as an item that has low discrimination power (Azwar, 2012)

Analysis of data used for testing hypotheses using product moment correlation analysis techniques from person. Reason researchers use this analysis because it can be used to test the relationship between independent variables (x) with dependent variables (y). Data analysis using the SPSS 17.00 program.

IV. RESULTS

From the results obtained there is a relationship between emotional regulation of self-acceptance of 0.681 with a significant 0.00. meaning that the higher the regulation of emotions in prisoners, the better the self-acceptance of inmates. Conversely, the lower the regulation of prisoners' emotions, the lower their self-acceptance of inmates.

Based on the data obtained, reappraisal has a hypothetical mean of 29.72 with a standard deviation of 98.89. whereas at the suppression mean hypothetically 19.64 with a standard deviation of 6,026.

Another research finding that strengthens this research is the study by Aris & Rinaldi (2015) that there is a significant positive correlation between emotional regulation and self-acceptance of premenopausal women. This can be interpreted that the higher the regulation of emotions, the higher self-

acceptance will be. Conversely the lower the regulation of emotions, the lower the self-acceptance of premenopausal women.

Based on the hypothetical mean and standard deviation that has been obtained, the regulation of emotion regulation can be categorized. It can be explained that of the 288 inmates who used emotion regulation strategies as many as 187 people in the sense that inmates changed their views on a context. While inmates who used suppression strategies as many as 101 people in terms of prisoners more often by not showing emotion in their daily lives.

V. DISCUSSION

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study it can be concluded that there is a positive relationship between emotional regulation and self-acceptance of inmates. This means that the higher the regulation of emotions, the higher the self-acceptance of inmates. Conversely, the lower self-acceptance, the lower self-acceptance.

The magnitude of the contribution of emotional regulation to self-acceptance of prisoners is in the moderate category. Judging from the results of the study there are still several other factors such as age, background, prison period, education etc.

Suggestion

Based on the findings of this study, some suggestions can be given:

1. Prisoners need to have good emotional regulation when facing new pressures and situations in the prison environment. Changes that occur during imprisonment such as loss of freedom, far from relatives, narrow cells result in emotional instability in prisoners. Therefore positive regulation of emotions is needed so that prisoners are able to display positive behavior.
2. For further researchers who want to reexamine emotional regulation or self-acceptance of inmates, while involving other factors such as education level, age, length of detention period as one of the research variables.
3. At the research site, especially the class IIA Aceh Central detention center, it is recommended that more attention be paid to prisoners who have poor emotion regulation. Activities are held that can channel or transfer emotional regulation such as creativity training or relaxation training so that prisoners have more positive emotional regulation and good self-acceptance.

REFERENCES

- [1] Anindita & Dahlan, W. W. (2008). Pengalaman dan penghayatan seorang mantan narapidana terhadap kehidupan di penjara. *Jurnal Psikologi Sosial*, 14(3), 243-251.
- [2] Aris,D.P. Rinaldi. (2015). Hubungan Regulasi Emosi Dengan Penerimaan Diri Wanita Premenopause. *Jurnal Volume 6 No.1*
- [3] Bull, R., Cooke, R., Hatcher, R., Woodhams, J., Biby, C., & Grant, T. (2006). *Criminal Psychology*. England: Oneworld.
- [4] Bartol, C. L. (1994). *Psychology and Law*. California: Wadsworth Inc.
- [5] Ceyhan, A. A. & Ceyhan, E. (2011). Investigation of University Students' Self-acceptance and Learned Resourcefulness: A Longitudinal Study. *High Education*. 61, 649-661.
- [6] Chaplin, J.P. 2004. *Kamus Lengkap Psikologi*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
- [7] Cronbach, L. J. 1963. *Educational Psychology*. New York: Harcourt, Brace & World, Inc.
- [8] Dariyo Agoes.(2007). *Psikologi perkembangan anak usia tiga tahun pertama*,Jakarta; PT Refika Aditama.Hal:205
- [9] Germer, C. K. 2009. *The Mindful Path To Self-Compassion*. USA: The Guilford Press.
- [10] Gurung, R. A. R. (2006). *Health psychology : A cultural approach*. Canada: Thomson Wadsworth
- [11] Gussak, D. (2007). Comparing the Effectiveness of Art Therapy on Depression and Locus of Control on Male and Female Inmates. *The Arts in Psychotherapy*.
- [12] Gussak, D. (2009). The Effects of Art Therapy on Male and Female Inmates : Advancing the Research Base. *The Arts in Psychotherapy*
- [13] Gross, J. J. *The Emerging Field of Emotion Regulation: An Integrative Review of General Psychology Vol. 2 no. 3*, 1998.
- [14] James J. Gross, *Emotion Regulation: Past, Present, Future, Cognition and Emotion Vol. 13 no. 5*, 1999.
- [15] Gross dan Thompson, *Handbook of Emotion Regulation*, Guilford Press, New York, 2007.
- [16] Gross, J.J. and R.A. Thompson. *Emotion Regulation: Conceptual Foundation, Handbook of Emotion Regulation*, New York, 2006.
- [17] Gross, J.J. & John, O.P. (2003). Individual Differences in Two Emotion Regulation Processes: Implication for Affect, Relationship and Well-Being.
- [18] Gross, T. J. (2007). *Handbook of Emotion Regulation*. New York: The Guilford Press.
- [19] Hawari. (2011). *Manajemen Stres, Cemas dan Depresi.*, Jakarta.
- [20] Hadjam, M. N. R. (2014). Studi eksplorasi lapas Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta. Hibah penelitian Fakultas Psikologi UGM yang tidak dipublikasikan. UGM: CPMH.
- [21] Hurlock, Elizabeth. 1996. *Psikologi Perkembangan Suatu Pendekatan Sepanjang - Rentang Kehidupan*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [22] Jessica, C. S. (2015). Hubungan karakteristik Remaja di pontianak. *jurnal luntan .vol 3.No 1*.
- [23] Jersild, Arthur. T. 1978. *The Psychology of Adolescence*. New York: Mac millan Publishing Co.
- [24] Kubler-Ross, E. (1998). *On death and dying (Kematian sebagai bagian kehidupan)*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- [25] Kartono, K. (2011). *Patologi sosial*. Jakarta: Rajawali.
- [26] Kemenkumham. (2010). Undang Undang Nomor 12 Tahun 1995 Tentang Pemasarakatan. Retrieved April 19, 2014, from http://www.kemenkumham.go.id/attachments/article/167/uu12_1995.pdf
- [27] Lawler, K.A., Younger, J.W., Piferi, R.L., Billington, E., Jobe, R., Edmondson, K., & Jones, W.H. (2003). A change of heart: Cardiovascular correlates of forgiveness in response to interpersonal conflict. *Journal of Behavioral Medicine*, 26(5), 373-393.
- [28] Lawler, K.A., Younger, J.W., Piferi, R.L., Jobe, R.L., Edmondson, K.A., Jones, W.H. (2005). The unique effects of forgiveness on health: An exploration of pathways. *Journal of Behavioral Medicine*, 28(2), 157-167.
- [29] Lawrence, C. & Andrew, K. (2004). The influence of perceived prison crowding on Male inmates' perception of aggressive events. *Aggressive behavior*, 30, 273-283.
- [30] Lightsey, O. R., & Boyraz, G. (2011). Do positive thinking and meaning mediate the positive affect—life satisfaction relationship?. *Canadian Journal of Behavioral Science*, 43 (3), 203- 213. DOI: 10.1037/a0023150.
- [31] Luh Putu. (2017) Penerimaan Diri Dan Kecemasan Terhadap Status Narapidana. *Jurnal Psikologi Ilmiah Intuisi 9 (3) Universitas Negeri Semarang*
- [32] Mathews D.Wayne(1993). *Acceptance of self and other*. North Carolina Cooperative Extension Service.
- [33] Mulyadi, Lilik. 2005. *Pengadilan Anak di Indonesia: Teori, Praktik dan Permasalahannya*. Bandung: Mandar Maju.
- [34] Nevid, J. S., Rathus, S. A., & Greene, B. (2003). *Psikologi Abnormal*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [35] Pusat data Direktorat Jenderal Pemasarakatan, Kementerian Hukum dan HAM 2017.
- [36] Pusat data dan Informasi Lapas kelas IIA Takengon, 2017.
- [37] Putri, A. K & Hamidah. (2012). Hubungan antara Penerimaan Diri dengan Depresi pada Wanita Perimenopause. *Jurnal Psikologi Klinis dan*

- Kesehatan Mental. Vol 1. No 2. Fakultas Psikologi Universitas Airlangga Surabaya.
- [38] Poerwandari, K. (2011). Pendekatan Kualitatif untuk Penelitian Perilaku Manusia. Jakarta: LPSP3, Universitas Indonesia.
- [39] Rivlin, A., Hawton, K., Marzano, L., & Fazel, S. (2010). Psychiatric disorders in male prisoners who made near-lethal suicide attempts: Case-control study. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*. DOI: 10.1192/bjp.bp.110.077883.
- [40] Sarafino, E. P., & Smith, T. W. (2011). *Health psychology : Biopsychosocial interactions* (7th ed.). United States of America : John Willey & Sons Inc.
- [41] Salamah. (2005). Kondisi psikis dan alternatif penanganan masalah kesejahteraan sosial lansia di panti wredha. *Jurnal PKS* vol. IV No 11. (98-99) PGRI Yogyakarta.
- [42] Schultz, Duane. 1991. *Psikologi Pertumbuhan: Model-model Kepribadian Sehat*. Yogyakarta: Kanisius.
- [43] Sheridan, C. L., & Radmacher, S. A. 2013. *Health psychology: Challenging the biomedical model*. Singapore: John Wiley and Sons, Inc
- [44] Silawaty, I., & Ramdhan., M. (2007). Peran agama terhadap penyesuaian diri narapidana di dalam lembaga pemasyarakatan. *JPS*, 13, (03).
- [45] Siswati, T.I & Abdurrohlim. (2009). Masa Hukuman & Stres Pada Narapidana. *Jurnal Proyeksi*. 04(02), 95-106.
- [46] Smet, B. (1994). *Psikologi kesehatan*. Ahli bahasa: Bagus Wismanto. Jakarta: PT. Grasindo Persada.
- [47] Susilawati, Susi. 2002. Penyimpangan Beberapa Norma Kehidupan Ditinjau dari Sudut Sosiologi Hukum dan Pelaksanaan/Pembinaan Warga Binaan Masyarakat (November 2002) No. 2 Tahun III, *Warta Pemasyarakatan*.
- [48] Yogeve, K., Maya, T., & Jonathan, D. (2016). Self-Acceptance of Negative Emotions: The Positive Relationship With Effective Cognitive Reappraisal. *International Journal of Cognitive Therapy* , Vol. 9, No. 4, pp. 279-294.